

A STUDY OF UNEMPLOYMENT IN INDIAN ECONOMY

Dr. Sukhvir Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Commerce
SGTB Khalsa College, University of Delhi, Delhi

ABSTRACT:

Employment is an activity from which a person earns means of livelihood, i.e., income in cash or kind. Unemployment refers to a situation where the persons who are able to work and willing to work, fail to secure work or activity which gives them income or means of livelihood. The research has been done on the basis of data Analysis from CSO Report, Employment-Unemployment Survey in India and Five Years Plan and use of Charts and Graphs for better knowledge of the present situation, also unemployment rates in UPS and in percent. The study concluded that in India, a major portion of unemployment consists of seasonal and disguised unemployment in rural areas and open unemployment of educated people in towns and cities

Keyword: *Unemployment, disguised, seasonal*

INTRODUCTION

Employment is an activity from which a person earns means of livelihood, i.e., income in cash or kind. Those who fail to undertake any such activity which provides them income or means of living are categorised as unemployed. Usually unemployment and poverty go hand in hand, as persons who fail to earn living are likely to be poor. This does not, however, mean that all those who are employed are rich. Persons working in low productive occupations or doing petty jobs like domestic servants, or those engaged in menial activities may be fully employed, and yet be among the poor sections of society.

The problem of employment has three main aspects in India, viz.

1. Low rate of Labour force participation,
2. A Large part of Labour force is unemployed or underemployed, and
3. Productivity of those who are employed is very low.

Unemployment refers to a situation where the persons who are able to work and willing to work, fail to secure work or activity which gives them income or means of livelihood. From rational

economic point of view, only those persons who are actively seeking work (employment) but fail to get it are classified as unemployed. The words actively seeking work' are important to separate the categories of really unemployed persons from those who do not work nor do they actively seek work. Those who are fit to work but do not want to work and hence do not actively seek work are not included among the unemployed.

UNEMPLOYMENT

Unemployment refers to a situation where people who are able to work and willing to work, fail to secure work or activity which gives them income or means of livelihood. Technically speaking all people who do not have work cannot be categorized as unemployed. From stricter point of view people who are actively seeking for work but fail to get it are classified as unemployed. Unemployed individuals are those who are unable to earn money to meet financial obligations. Failure to pay mortgage payments or to pay rent may lead to homelessness through foreclosure or eviction. The loss of health insurance benefits that comes with unemployment increases susceptibility to malnutrition, illness, mental stress, and loss of self esteem leading to depression.

Quotes about UNEMPLOYMENT:

“A man’s labour is not only his capital but his life. When it passes, it returns never more. To utilize it, to prevent its wasteful squandering, to enable the poor man to bank it up for use hereafter, this surely is one of the most urgent tasks before civilization.”(**William Booth**)

“Mind unemployed in mind un-enjoyed” (Christian Nevell Bovee)

UNEMPLOYMENT RATE: As defined by the International Labour Organisation (ILO), “unemployed workers” are those who are currently working but are willing and able to work for pay, currently available to work, and have actively searched for work. Since not all unemployment may be open and counted by government agencies, official statistics on unemployment may not be accurate.

The ILO describes 4 different methods to calculate the unemployment rate:

- Labour force sample surveys are the most preferred method of unemployment rate calculation since they give the most comprehensive results and enables calculation of unemployment by different group categories such as race and gender.
- Official estimates statistics such as unemployment benefits, are computed based on the number of people insured representing the total labour force and the number of people insured that are collecting benefits. This method has been heavily criticized due to the expiration of benefits before the person finds work.
- Employment insurance statistics are the least effective being that they only include a month tally of unemployed people who enter employment offices. This method also includes unemployed who are not unemployed per the ILO definition.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In study by **Elliot (1996)** who examined that the long term unemployed becomes marginalized in society and alienated from due to the excessive poverty and their alienation may be dependent by their exclusion from the consumption culture which surrounds them. Furthermore, the findings revealed that the advertising could have unintended consequences on the unemployed by instilling a sense of inadequacy and self-denigration through the presentation of attainable, idealized images which may magnify their alienation, lower their feelings of self-esteem and damage their sense of identity.

Todaro, M.P., *Economic Development in the Third World*, Landman, Mew York, 1984, P.231, quoted by Dr.Alakn N. Sharma, *The Indian Journal of Labour Economics* — April - July - 1988.

Winefield, Triggerman, and Winefield (1991) studied social alienation and unemployment status in young adults. They revealed that young people social alienation is a consequence of unemployment rather than a predisposition towards it, but high social alienation at schools leads to later job dissatisfaction. In their study cross-sectional and longitudinal observation are reported from questionnaire survey of more than 300 South Australian school leavers and the questionnaire were administered before the participant had left school and again four years later, when they all left. This study attempted to identify the relationship between unsatisfactory workforce experiences and social alienation that found, those who were engaged in

unsatisfactory jobs and unemployed responded differently from those engaged in satisfactory jobs. A study conducted by Lane and Timothy (1999), found that women reported less social alienation than men. Similar findings were also confirmed by another study among the elderly men which reported greater feelings of alienation than women (**Calicchia& Barresi, 1975**).

Need of the Study: The unemployment scenario in India has always been quite acute. With a huge population and slow growth of job opportunities, unemployment has been widespread in India. Large scale unemployment has led to several socio-economic problems like poverty, malnutrition, antisocial and criminal activities, drug and substance abuse, etc. The lack of proper unemployment insurance schemes has further aggravated this problem.

Unemployment is one of the major reasons in macroeconomics for underdevelopment of Indian Economy. The increasing population and low job opportunities in the economy is the reason of lesser growth of GDP in India.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To analyse the trends of Unemployment in Indian Economy

- To evaluate the participation of Labour force on the basis of:
 - Age Groups
 - Sex

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the Present Study of Unemployment in India all the research has been done on the basis of:

1. Data Analysis from CSO Report, Employment-Unemployment Survey in India and Five Years Plan.

2. Use of Charts and Graphs for better knowledge of the present situation, also unemployment rates in UPS and in percent.

Analysis and Interpretation:

In the present study the data has been collected from various sources to analyse the trends. The things or data used are- Five year plans detailed summary in context of unemployment; reports,

charts and diagrams showing the unemployment rate. This will help us to know the extent of unemployment from recent times seen and how much affected the different areas on the bases of economic development, growth and economy as the whole. Also, how it has shown a change from last decade like unemployment rates, GDP, etc.

To evaluate the participation of Labour force:

In this aim we are focusing the decomposition of the unemployment burden on the basis of age groups and sex of the citizens.

- **On the basis of Age Groups:** The population of India is divided into three categories i.e., children or teenagers, adults and senior citizens. The analysis will be done that how much of the GDP is contributed by which age group by their productive work in the economy.

- **On the basis of Sex:** The males and females of the country are two main categories which are most of the time discriminated when employment is the topic either on the basis of pay or the job environment. This also helps to determine the unemployment in Indian Economy.

CONCLUSION: Unemployment refers to the condition where the aggregate demand for Labour is less than the aggregate supply of Labour so there is an increase in the proportion of the workforce actively seeking for work and they are unable to find it. It is a major cost to an economy not only in terms of opportunity cost but also in terms of social costs such as inequality, poverty, family problems, crime and social division. It is one of the major problems not only in Indian economy but most of the economies in the world. The main problem faced by the Indian economy in case of unemployment is the rate of development. Large-scale unemployment represents waste of human resources that could, if employed, make substantial addition to production and national income. Widespread unemployment is also a main cause of poverty in both rural as well as urban areas. Besides, loss of production and income unemployment is demoralizing for those who fail to secure any income earning activity and thus develops among them a feeling of being unwanted. Therefore, it is necessary to adopt urgent and effective measures to remove unemployment as speedily as possible.

Accelerating the growth of GDP with particular emphasis on the spread of income segments of the labour force could be a good strategy to generate employment. Pursuing suitable policies for education and skill development which would upgrade the quality of labour force and make it capable of supporting growth process which encourage labour absorption, especially in the organised sector would help in decreasing the rate of unemployment. In India, a major portion of unemployment consists of seasonal and disguised unemployment in rural areas and open unemployment of educated people in towns and cities. For rural unemployment, whether it is seasonal or disguised. The remedy lies in providing supplementary employment opportunities in the form of village industries, such as beekeeping, poultry, horticulture, khadi, animal husbandry, fisheries, handicrafts, etc., etc. Such activities will not only provide a supplementary source of income to the unemployed persons but also help in removing excessive population pressure from the land and thus enable agriculture to adopt modern methods of improvements in productivity. The remedy for urban educated unemployment lies in training, encouraging and helping the young educated persons in finding avenues of self-employment. Further, the education system should be vocationalised to produce workforce that is well- trained and well- equipped to take up the emerging work avenues in the rapidly growing economy. Special schemes for employment generation need to be launched in accordance with the resource position and requirements of specific areas as well as the needs and capabilities of specific groups and categories of unemployed persons. However, some overall policy measures that can be suggested for meeting the unemployment situation in India are overhauling education system, Rapid Economic Growth, Population control, Development of village and small industries.

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